

EVOLUTION OF CUISINE TERMINOLOGY ACROSS CULTURES

Parascovia CAZACU, Gabriela SAGANEAN

Moldova State University

ORCID: 0000-0002-7291-3138, ORCID: 0000-0001-7772-2405

Cuisine terminology is an essential part of a cultural identity. The evolution of cuisine terminology refers to the changes that have occurred in the language used to describe food, cooking techniques, ingredients, and culinary traditions over time. It has been shaped by various factors, including globalization, migration, technology, and changing cultural attitudes toward food. Globalization has been a critical factor in the evolution of cuisine terminology, as it has brought people from different cultures together, leading to the introduction of new terms and vocabulary. By moving from one country to another, people have brought their food traditions and adapted them to the new surroundings. Similarly, technology has had a decisive influence on food distribution, leading to the introduction of new terms describing different types of food outlets. New definitions and terminology have been developed to describe the various kinds of food and eating habits, thanks to increasing health awareness and recognition of the environmental impact of food production. As these attitudes continue to evolve, cuisine terminology will likely continue to change and adapt to these changes. The evolution of cuisine terminology reflects the dynamic nature of our world and the diversity of our food traditions and practices. Moreover, it has given rise to a better understanding and appreciation of diverse cuisines, encouraging innovation and sustainability in the food industry as well as preserving culinary traditions and cultural heritage.

Keywords: *terminology, cuisine, evolution, culture, diversity.*

EVOLUȚIA TERMINOLOGIEI CULINARE ÎN DIFERITE CIVILIZAȚII

Terminologia bucătăriei este o parte esențială a unei identități culturale. Evoluția terminologiei culinare se referă la schimbările care au avut loc în limbajul folosit pentru a descrie mâncarea, tehnicile de gătit, ingredientele și tradițiile culinare de-a lungul timpului. Acesta a fost modelată de diverși factori, inclusiv globalizare, migrația, tehnologia și schimbarea atitudinilor culturale față de alimente. Globalizarea a fost un factor critic în evoluția terminologiei culinare, deoarece a reunit oameni din culturi diferite, ducând la introducerea de noi termeni și vocabular. În mod similar, tehnologia a avut o influență decisivă asupra distribuției alimentelor, ducând la introducerea de noi

termeni care descriu diferite tipuri de magazine alimentare. Datorită creșterii conștientizării sănătății și recunoașterii impactului asupra mediului al producției alimentare, noi definiții și termeni au apărut pentru a descrie diferitele tipuri de alimente și obiceiuri culinare. Pe măsură ce aceste atitudini continuă să evolueze, terminologia bucătăriei va continua probabil să se schimbe și să se adapteze la aceste schimbări. Astfel, evoluția acestui tip de terminologie reflectă natura dinamică a lumii noastre și diversitatea tradițiilor și practicilor noastre culinare. Mai mult, ea a dat naștere la o mai bună înțelegere și apreciere a diverselor bucătării, încurajând inovația și sustenabilitatea în industria alimentară, precum și păstrarea tradițiilor culinare și a moștenirii culturale.

Cuvinte-cheie: *terminologie, bucătărie, evoluție, cultură, diversitate.*

Food is a universal language that transcends borders and connects people. However, the terminology used to describe food can vary greatly from one culture to another. The evolution of cuisine terminology across cultures is a fascinating subject that sheds light on the way we view and experience food.

The cuisine terminology is shaped by various factors, including historical events, migration, cultural influences, and technological advancements. One of the earliest examples of the evolution of cuisine terminology can be seen in the Ancient Egyptian civilization. Hieroglyphics found on ancient tombs depict the use of various spices and herbs in their cuisine. The terms used to describe these ingredients were often based on their medicinal properties, reflecting the belief in the healing power of food.

In medieval Europe, the cuisine terminology was influenced by the aristocracy's lavish banquets and the emergence of guilds of chefs who developed new culinary techniques. In particular French cuisine had a significant impact on the evolution of cuisine terminology during that time. Terms like "*sous vide*," "*sauté*," and "*braise*" were developed to describe French culinary techniques that are still used today.

The Age of Exploration in the 15th and 16th centuries introduced new ingredients and flavors to European cuisine, leading to the development of new cuisine terminology. For example, the introduction of chili peppers from the Americas to Europe led to the development of terms like "*paprika*" and "*cayenne pepper*" to describe these new spicy ingredients.

As global trade increased in the 19th and 20th centuries, cuisine terminology continued to evolve at an accelerated pace. Asian cuisine had a significant impact on the evolution of cuisine terminology during this time.

Terms like "wasabi," "soy sauce" and "umami" are all examples of Asian culinary terms that have become widely recognized in Western cultures.

In recent years, the rise of fusion cuisine has led to the introduction of new cuisine terminology to describe these innovative and eclectic dishes. Terms like "fusion," "pan-Asian" and "New American" have become increasingly common in the culinary lexicon.

Migration has a profound influence on cuisine terminology, shaping and enriching the culinary lexicon of different regions and cultures. When people migrate from one place to another, they bring with them their culinary traditions, ingredients, and cooking techniques, which often lead to the creation of new dishes and the evolution of existing ones [1]. This cross-pollination of culinary practices and flavors introduces new terminology into the culinary landscape. Here are a few ways in which migration influences cuisine terminology:

1. When people settle in a new country or region, they often adapt their traditional recipes to incorporate local ingredients and cooking methods. This process frequently involves *borrowing terms* from the local language to describe the newly created dishes or variations. For example, the migration of Italians to the United States led to the creation of dishes like *spaghetti and meatballs*, which borrowed the term "spaghetti" from Italian cuisine and combined it with "meatballs", a term more commonly used in English. A further instance could be "kimchi fried rice", where kimchi is a traditional Korean side dish made of fermented vegetables, most commonly cabbage, seasoned with spices, which is added to fried rice along with other ingredients like vegetables, meat, and soy sauce. In such a way Korean immigrants adapted their traditional recipes to incorporate local ingredients and flavors, like in the United States.

2. Migration can also lead to the *transliteration* or transcription of culinary terms from one language to another. As migrants bring their food culture to a new place, they may need to find linguistic equivalents for their ingredients and dishes. Sometimes, this involves adapting the pronunciation and spelling of the original terms to fit the phonetic system of the new language. For instance, the Indian dish "biryani" has been transliterated and transcribed into various languages, resulting in different spellings and pronunciations, such as "biryani" or "briyani". Another example is the popular Greek dish "γάρος" (pronounced "yee-rohs"), a term that was transcribed into English using the Greek alphabet "gyro", simplifying the pronunciation for English speakers..

3. Migration often results in the fusion of different culinary traditions, leading to the creation of hybrid dishes and culinary styles. As different cultures come into contact, their cuisines interact, giving rise to new flavors, techniques, and terminologies. For example, the fusion of *Mexican* and *American cuisines* in the southwestern United States has given birth to dishes like "Tex-Mex". Along with the fusion of flavors, Tex-Mex cuisine also has its own unique culinary terminology. For instance, dishes like "*enchiladas*" (rolled tortillas filled with meat, cheese, or beans, and topped with chili sauce) and "*quesadillas*" (tortillas filled with cheese and other ingredients, folded, and grilled) have become popular Tex-Mex staples. Moreover, the term "*curry pizza*" represents the blending of Indian and Italian culinary flavors. This fusion dish combines the spiciness of Indian curry with the popular Italian pizza. It typically features a pizza crust topped with curry sauce, along with a variety of toppings such as chicken, vegetables, and cheese.

4. When people from different cultures meet, new ingredients and cooking techniques can be shared and this fact requires the development of new culinary terminology. As these ingredients and techniques become integrated into the local cuisine, new terms are coined to describe them. For instance, the migration of Asian communities to Western countries popularized ingredients like *tofu*, *wasabi*, *mochi* and *bok choy*, necessitating the adoption of these terms in local culinary vocabularies.

5. Migration not only influences the terminology used for dishes but also impacts the names of restaurants, cafes, and food establishments. Migrants often establish businesses that reflect their cultural heritage and serve as gathering places for their communities. These establishments often bear names that reflect the migrants' origin, using terms and phrases from their native languages. In this case, a Japanese restaurant owner may choose a name that reflects their Japanese origins. They could opt for a term like "*Sakura Sushi*," where "*Sakura*" refers to cherry blossoms, a symbol strongly associated with Japan. By incorporating "*Sushi*" in the name, they indicate the type of cuisine they specialize in, attracting sushi enthusiasts and those interested in Japanese cuisine. For instance, a group of Lebanese migrants opens a restaurant in a new country instead of choosing a generic name, they opt for "*Mazaat Al-Sham*," which translates to "Flavors of the Levant" in Arabic. The term "*Mazaat*" refers to an assortment of small dishes, similar to tapas or meze, which is a common element of Lebanese cuisine. "*Al-Sham*" refers to the region

encompassing Lebanon, Syria, Jordan, and Palestine, known for its vibrant culinary traditions. This practice not only preserves cultural identity but also contributes to the diversity of cuisine terminology in the new location.

In support of those already stated, the opening of Chinois-on-Main in Santa Monica, California, in 1983 is credited as being the beginning of cross-cultural cuisine [2]. However, the media attention toward cross-cultural cuisine did not become prolific until 1987. One of the early advocates of this cuisine was Ken Hom. He explained that the pairing of multiple nationalities of foods was a natural progression from the favoring of singular ethnic cuisines. The techniques and ingredients from China, France, Japan, and Italy are borrowed and lent to create composite dishes. He indicated that the fusion of many cuisines was not a fad, but a continually evolving style of cooking that is being explored by food service operators[4] . F. Fabricant echoed Hom's opinions, agreeing that cross-cultural cuisine may be the most persistent and enduring food trend of the decade [3]. In her columns, Fabricant has consistently referred to cross-cultural cuisine as a trend.

The attention given to cross-cultural cuisine continued to build during the following years. F. Fabricant contends that "even if some of the ingredients do not speak the same native tongue, they should be suited to each other [2]. It is often these poorly combined dishes, nicknamed victims of the "chop suey-burrito syndrome," that discourage consumers' interest in cross-cultural cuisine. However, the appearance of many new and different restaurants producing cross-cultural cuisine seems to indicate that it is, and will be, a continuing trend.

Technological advancements have also played a key role in the evolution of cuisine terminology, as new tools and techniques have been developed to aid in food preparation and cooking. Moreover, these advancements have transformed the culinary landscape by facilitating global communication, introducing new food processing and preservation methods, driving culinary movements, shaping kitchen appliances and tools, and influencing food presentation and photography. Through the internet and social media, culinary knowledge has been shared worldwide, leading to the incorporation of diverse cooking techniques, ingredients, and flavors into mainstream culinary vocabulary [6]. There have been many technological advancements in cuisine in recent years, including:

1. *Molecular gastronomy*, a scientific approach to cooking, which involves using modern technology and techniques to create new and innovative dishes. Techniques like *spherification*- which involves creating small spheres or "caviar" of liquid ingredients, *foams*- which involves using ingredients like soy lecithin or gelatin to transform liquid components into light and airy foam textures, and *gels*- which involve transforming liquids into solid or semi-solid textures while retaining their original flavors, are used to create unique textures and flavors. These three examples showcase the scientific and innovative approach of molecular gastronomy, where chefs utilize modern techniques and ingredients to push the boundaries of traditional cooking and create visually stunning and unique dining experiences.

2. *Sous vide cooking* is a cooking technique where food is vacuum-sealed in a plastic bag and cooked in a water bath at a precise temperature. This method highlights precise temperature control, consistent results, and enhanced flavors and textures. By utilizing this technique, chefs can elevate the quality of their dishes and create restaurant-worthy meals with minimal effort.

3. *3D food printing* allows chefs to create intricate and complex shapes and designs with food. It can revolutionize the culinary world by offering intricate and customizable food designs, reducing food waste, and expanding creative possibilities for chefs. This technology has the potential to transform the way food is prepared and presented, leading to unique dining experiences and greater sustainability in the industry.

4. *Smart kitchen appliances* can monitor and adjust cooking temperatures and times, as well as alert you when you're running low on ingredients. Moreover, through the app, individuals can set cooking programs, timers, and temperature settings, ensuring precise and consistent cooking results. Thus, smart kitchen appliances integrate technology to improve cooking precision, convenience, and efficiency. By incorporating features such as *remote control*, *monitoring*, and *intelligent functionalities*, these appliances offer enhanced user experiences and simplify various aspects of meal preparation and management.

5. *Robots* are being developed that can chop, mix, and even cook meals. The integration of robotics in the kitchen holds the potential to enhance efficiency, accuracy, and productivity in food preparation. By automating repetitive tasks and working alongside human chefs, these robots can optimize workflow, reduce labor-intensive activities, and enable culinary professionals to

devote more time and attention to creativity, innovation, and providing exceptional dining experiences.

With innovative techniques like molecular gastronomy and 3D food printing, chefs can explore new realms of culinary creativity, pushing boundaries and surprising diners with unique textures and flavors. The integration of smart kitchen appliances enhances efficiency and productivity, allowing chefs to focus on creative aspects while automation takes care of repetitive tasks. Furthermore, these advancements make food more accessible by enabling customization to cater to individual dietary needs and preferences. Ultimately, these technological advancements contribute to a more enjoyable and inclusive culinary experience for people from all walks of life.

The evolution of cuisine terminology holds significant influence over cultural attitudes toward food. By expanding culinary vocabulary, promoting cultural exchange and fusion, emphasizing conscious food choices, highlighting health and well-being, and encouraging culinary creativity and innovation, cuisine terminology shapes cultural perceptions and appreciation of food. It fosters a diverse, inclusive, and mindful food culture that celebrates culinary diversity, sustainability, health consciousness, and culinary innovation. As we continue to witness the evolution of cuisine terminology, its impact on cultural attitudes toward food will remain a driving force behind the transformation of our culinary experiences and perspectives.

Modern cuisine terminology places a growing emphasis on ingredients and their sourcing. Terms such as "*local*," "*organic*," "*sustainable*," and "*fair trade*" have gained prominence. This shift in terminology highlights the importance of conscious food choices, including supporting local farmers, considering environmental impact, and prioritizing ethical sourcing. Such terminology shapes cultural attitudes by encouraging a more mindful and responsible approach to food consumption, promoting sustainability and ethical considerations.

It must be taken into account the fact that the evolution of cuisine terminology has witnessed an increased focus on health and well-being. Terms like "*clean eating*," "*plant-based*," "*gluten-free*," and "*vegan*" have gained popularity, reflecting a heightened awareness of the link between food and health. This terminology encourages cultural attitudes that prioritize nutritious and wholesome food choices, fostering a greater emphasis on well-being and

healthier lifestyles. It contributes to a culture where individuals become more conscious of the impact of food on their physical and mental well-being.

To conclude, it is obvious that the evolution of cuisine terminology has undergone significant changes throughout history. The terminology used to describe different types of cuisine has evolved in response to cultural, social, and technological developments, as well as global influences and culinary innovations. However, as societies became more interconnected through trade, exploration, and immigration, culinary influences began to blend, leading to the emergence of fusion cuisines and the need for new terminology to describe these hybrid culinary styles [5].

After considering the diverse range of cuisines and cultures around the world, it is clear that there is a great deal of variation in the terminology used to describe food and cooking techniques. Moreover, it is important to recognize and respect the diversity of cuisine terminology across cultures, and to understand the cultural significance of different culinary traditions. This can enhance our appreciation and enjoyment of food, and foster cross-cultural understanding and respect.

References:

1. BROOKS K. G. and Bosker G., *The G.lobal Kitchen*, Kansas City: Andrews and McMeel, 1981.
2. FABRICANT F., *Culinary Trends: East Meets West Meets North Meets South*, *Nation's Restaurant News*, (October 23, 1989, p. 8.
3. FABRICANT F., *East Meets West by Mixing Ingredients, Styles of Both Worlds*, *Nation's Restaurant News*, September 7, 1987, p. 11.
4. HORN K., *East Meets West Cuisine*, New York: Simon and Schuster, 1987.
5. MONTANARI, M. *Food Is Culture*, Columbia University Press, 2009.
6. TRINCONI, F. *The Impact of Technology on Gastronomy and Culinary Tourism*. *Journal of Gastronomy and Tourism*, 5(1), 2020, p. 23-36.